

An Application of Differential Subordination to Analytic Functions

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Abstract—In the present paper, using the technique of differential subordination, we obtain certain results for analytic functions defined by a multiplier transformation in the open unit disc $\mathbb{E} = \{z : |z| < 1\}$. We claim that our results extend and generalize the existing results in this particular direction.

Keywords—Analytic function, Differential subordination, Multiplier transformation.

I. INTRODUCTION

LET $\mathcal{A}_p$ denote the class of functions of the form

$$f(z) = z^p + \sum_{k=p+1}^{\infty} a_k z^k, \quad p \in \mathbb{N} = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\},$$

which are analytic in the open unit disc $\mathbb{E} = \{z : |z| < 1\}$. We write $\mathcal{A}_1 = \mathcal{A}$.

A function $f \in \mathcal{A}$ is said to be starlike of order α ($0 \leq \alpha < 1$) if it satisfies the condition

$$\Re \left(\frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} \right) > \alpha, \quad z \in \mathbb{E}.$$

Let $\mathcal{S}^*(\alpha)$ denote the class of starlike functions of order α . We write $\mathcal{S}^*(0) = \mathcal{S}^*$, therefore, $\mathcal{S}^*$ is the class of starlike functions (w.r.t. origin).

For $f \in \mathcal{A}_p$, we define the multiplier transformation $I_p(n, \alpha)$ as

$$I_p(n, \alpha)[f](z) = z^p + \sum_{k=p+1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{k+\alpha}{p+\alpha} \right)^n a_k z^k, \quad (\alpha \geq 0, n \in \mathbb{Z}).$$

The operator $I_p(n, \alpha)$ has been recently studied by Aghalary et al. [9]. Earlier, the operator $I_1(n, \alpha)$ was investigated by Cho and Srivastava [7] and Cho and Kim [8], whereas the operator $I_1(n, 1)$ was studied by Uralgaddi and Somanatha [1]. $I_1(n, 0)$ is the well-known Sălăgean ([5]) derivative operator D^n , defined as:

$$D^n[f](z) = z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k^n a_k z^k,$$

where $n \in \mathbb{N}_0 = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and $f \in \mathcal{A}$.

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A function $f \in \mathcal{A}$ is said to belong to the class $\mathcal{S}_n(\alpha)$ if it satisfies the condition

$$\Re \left(\frac{D^{n+1}[f](z)}{D^n[f](z)} \right) > \alpha, \quad z \in \mathbb{E}.$$

In 1989, the class $\mathcal{S}_n(\alpha)$ has been studied by Owa, Shen and Obradović [10].

Uralgaddi [2] proved if $f(z) = z + a_{m+1}z^{m+1} + a_{m+2}z^{m+2} + \dots \in \mathcal{S}_n(0)$ for some $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, then

$$\Re \left(\frac{D^n[f](z)}{z} \right)^{\frac{1}{n+1}} > \frac{1}{2}, \quad z \in \mathbb{E}.$$

Recently, Li and Owa [6], proved the following results:

Theorem 1.1: Let $f(z) = z + a_{m+1}z^{m+1} + a_{m+2}z^{m+2} + \dots$, be analytic in $\mathbb{E}$ and satisfy the condition

$$\Re \left(\frac{D^{n+1}[f](z)}{D^n[f](z)} \right) > \frac{2 - m(n+1)}{2}, \quad z \in \mathbb{E}$$

for some $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$. Then

$$\Re \left(\frac{D^n[f](z)}{z} \right)^{\frac{1}{n+1}} > \frac{1}{2}, \quad z \in \mathbb{E}.$$

Theorem 1.2: If $f(z) = z + a_{m+1}z^{m+1} + a_{m+2}z^{m+2} + \dots \in \mathcal{S}_n(\alpha)$ for some $\alpha, 0 \leq \alpha < 1, n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $m \in \mathbb{N}$, then for any $\beta, 0 < \beta \leq \frac{2}{2(1-\alpha)}$, the sharp estimate is

$$\Re \left(\frac{D^n[f](z)}{z} \right)^{\beta} > 2^{\frac{2\beta(\alpha-1)}{m}}, \quad z \in \mathbb{E}.$$

The main objective of the present paper is to generalize certain existing results stated above using differential subordination and find the corresponding generalized results for multiplier transformation $I_p(n, \alpha)$ in the subordination form.

II. PRELIMINARIES

We shall need the following definitions and lemmas to prove our results.

Definition 2.1: Let f and g be analytic in $\mathbb{E}$. We say that f is subordinate to g in $\mathbb{E}$, written as $f(z) \prec g(z)$ in $\mathbb{E}$, if g is univalent in $\mathbb{E}$, $f(0) = g(0)$ and $f(\mathbb{E}) \subset g(\mathbb{E})$.

Definition 2.2: Let $h : \mathbb{C}^2 \times \mathbb{E} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ and let h be univalent in $\mathbb{E}$. If p is analytic in $\mathbb{E}$ and satisfies the differential subordination

$$(p(z), zp'(z); z) \prec h(z), \quad (p(0), 0; 0) = h(0), \quad (1)$$

then p is called a solution of the differential subordination (1). The univalent function q is called a dominant of the differential subordination (1) if $p \prec q$ for all p satisfying (1). A dominant $\tilde{q}$ that satisfies $\tilde{q} \prec q$ for all dominants q of (1), is said to be the best dominant of (1).

Definition 2.3: A function $L(z, t), z \in \mathbb{E}$ and $t \geq 0$ is said to be a subordination chain if $L(\cdot, t)$ is analytic and univalent in $\mathbb{E}$ for all $t \geq 0$, $L(z, \cdot)$ is continuously differentiable on $[0, \infty)$ for all $z \in \mathbb{E}$ and $L(z, t_1) \prec L(z, t_2)$ for all $0 \leq t_1 \leq t_2$.

Lemma 2.4: ([3, page 159]). The function $L(z, t) : \mathbb{E} \times [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, of the form $L(z, t) = a_1(t)z + \dots$ with $a_1(t) \neq 0$ for all $t \geq 0$, and $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} |a_1(t)| = \infty$, is said to be a subordination chain if and only if $\Re \left[\frac{z L/z}{L/t} \right] > 0$ for all $z \in \mathbb{E}$ and $t \geq 0$.

Lemma 2.5: ([12]). Let F be analytic in $\mathbb{E}$ and let G be analytic and univalent in $\mathbb{E}$ except for points z_0 such that $\lim_{z \rightarrow z_0} G(z) = \infty$, with $F(0) = G(0)$. If $F \not\prec G$ in $\mathbb{E}$, then there is a point $z_0 \in \mathbb{E}$ and $z_0 \in \partial\mathbb{E}$ (boundary of $\mathbb{E}$) such that $F(|z| < |z_0|) \subset G(\mathbb{E})$, $F(z_0) = G(z_0)$ and $z_0 F'(z_0) = m z_0 G'(z_0)$ for some $m \geq 1$.

III. MAIN RESULTS

The following result is essentially due to Miller and Mocanu [13, page 76]. For the completeness of our results, we also prove it here with an alternative proof using subordination chain.

Theorem 3.1: Let $q, q(z) \neq 0, z \in \mathbb{E}$, be a univalent function such that $\frac{zq'(z)}{q(z)}$ is starlike in $\mathbb{E}$. If an analytic function $P, P(z) \neq 0, z \in \mathbb{E}$, satisfies the differential subordination

$$\frac{zP'(z)}{P(z)} \prec \frac{zq'(z)}{q(z)} = h(z), \quad (2)$$

then

$$P \prec q = \exp \left[\int_0^z \frac{h(t)}{t} dt \right],$$

and q is the best dominant.

Proof: Let us define h as

$$h(z) = \frac{zq'(z)}{q(z)}, \quad z \in \mathbb{E}. \quad (3)$$

Since h is starlike and hence univalent in $\mathbb{E}$. The subordination in (2) is, therefore, well-defined in $\mathbb{E}$.

We need to show that $P \prec q$. Suppose to the contrary that $P \not\prec q$ in $\mathbb{E}$. Then by Lemma 2.5, there exist points $z_0 \in \mathbb{E}$ and $z_0 \in \partial\mathbb{E}$ such that $P(z_0) = q(z_0)$ and $z_0 P'(z_0) = m z_0 q'(z_0)$, $m \geq 1$. Then

$$\frac{z_0 P'(z_0)}{P(z_0)} = \frac{m z_0 q'(z_0)}{q(z_0)}, \quad z \in \mathbb{E}. \quad (4)$$

Consider a function

$$L(z, t) = (1+t) \frac{zq'(z)}{q(z)}, \quad z \in \mathbb{E}. \quad (5)$$

The function $L(z, t)$ is analytic in $\mathbb{E}$ for all $t \geq 0$ and is continuously differentiable on $[0, \infty)$ for all $z \in \mathbb{E}$. Now,

$$a_1(t) = \left(\frac{L(z, t)}{z} \right)_{(0,t)} = (1+t) \frac{q'(0)}{q(0)}.$$

As q is univalent in $\mathbb{E}$, so, $q'(0) \neq 0$. Therefore, it follows that $a_1(t) \neq 0$ and $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} |a_1(t)| = \infty$. A simple calculation yields

$$\frac{z L/z}{L/t} = (1+t) \frac{zQ'(z)}{Q(z)}, \quad z \in \mathbb{E},$$

where $Q(z) = \frac{zq'(z)}{q(z)}$. Since Q is starlike in $\mathbb{E}$ and $t \geq 0$. Therefore, we obtain

$$\Re \left(\frac{z L/z}{L/t} \right) > 0, \quad z \in \mathbb{E}.$$

Hence, in view of Lemma 2.4, $L(z, t)$ is a subordination chain. Therefore, $L(z, t_1) \prec L(z, t_2)$ for $0 \leq t_1 \leq t_2$. From (5), we have $L(z, 0) = h(z)$, thus we deduce that $L(z, t) \in h(\mathbb{E})$ for $|z| = 1$ and $t \geq 0$. In view of (4) and (5), we can write

$$\frac{z_0 P'(z_0)}{P(z_0)} = L(z_0, m-1) \notin h(\mathbb{E}),$$

where $z_0 \in \mathbb{E}$, $|z_0| = 1$ and $m \geq 1$, which is a contradiction to (2). Hence,

$$P \prec q = \exp \left[\int_0^z \frac{h(t)}{t} dt \right].$$

This completes the proof of the theorem. ■

Theorem 3.2: Let h be starlike univalent in $\mathbb{E}$ with $h(0) = 0$. Let $f \in \mathcal{A}_p$ satisfy

$$\frac{I_p(n+1, \lambda)[f](z)}{I_p(n, \lambda)[f](z)} - 1 \prec h(z), \quad z \in \mathbb{E}, \quad (6)$$

then

$$\left(\frac{I_p(n, \lambda)[f](z)}{z^p} \right)^\beta \prec q(z) = \exp \left[(\rho + p) \int_0^z \frac{h(t)}{t} dt \right],$$

for $z \in \mathbb{E}$, $\beta > 0$. The function q is the best dominant.

Proof: Let us write

$$\left(\frac{I_p(n, \lambda)[f](z)}{z^p} \right)^\beta = r(z), \quad z \in \mathbb{E}. \quad (7)$$

Differentiate (7) logarithmically, we obtain

$$\frac{z I_p'(n, \lambda)[f](z)}{I_p(n, \lambda)[f](z)} - p = \frac{zr'(z)}{r(z)}, \quad z \in \mathbb{E}. \quad (8)$$

A little calculation yields the following equality

$$z I_p'(n, \lambda)[f](z) = (\rho + p) I_p(n+1, \lambda)[f](z) - I_p(n, \lambda)[f](z), \quad (9)$$

By making use of (9), from (6) and (8), we have

$$\frac{I_p(n+1, \lambda)[f](z)}{I_p(n, \lambda)[f](z)} - 1 = \frac{1}{(\rho + p)} \frac{zr'(z)}{r(z)} \prec h(z).$$

As $p \in \mathbb{N}$, $\alpha \geq 0$ and by our assumption, $\lambda > 0$. Therefore, we have $(\alpha + p) > 0$. Now in view of Theorem 3.1, we obtain

$$\left(\frac{I_p(n, \alpha)[f](z)}{z^p} \right)^\beta = r(z) \prec q(z), z \in \mathbb{E},$$

where $q(z) = \exp \left[(\alpha + p) \int_0^z \frac{h(t)}{t} dt \right]$, it completes the proof. ■

IV. APPLICATIONS TO ANALYTIC FUNCTIONS

For $h(z) = \frac{2(1-\alpha)z}{1-z}$, where $\alpha \neq 1$, is a real number. It is easy to check that h is starlike in $\mathbb{E}$. When we make this selection of h in Theorem 3.2, we get the following result.

Corollary 4.1: If $f \in \mathcal{A}_p$ satisfies

$$\frac{I_p(n+1, \alpha)[f](z)}{I_p(n, \alpha)[f](z)} \prec \frac{1+(1-2\alpha)z}{1-z}, z \in \mathbb{E},$$

then

$$\left(\frac{I_p(n, \alpha)[f](z)}{z^p} \right)^\beta \prec (1-z)^{2\beta(\alpha-1)(\lambda+p)}, z \in \mathbb{E},$$

where $\alpha \neq 1$, $\lambda > 0$, are real numbers.

If we put $p = 1$, $\lambda = 0$ in Corollary 4.1, we have the following result.

Corollary 4.2: If $f \in \mathcal{A}$ satisfies

$$\frac{D^{n+1}[f](z)}{D^n[f](z)} \prec \frac{1+(1-2\alpha)z}{1-z}, z \in \mathbb{E},$$

then

$$\left(\frac{D^n[f](z)}{z} \right)^\beta \prec (1-z)^{2\beta(\alpha-1)}, z \in \mathbb{E},$$

where $\alpha \neq 1$, $\lambda > 0$, are real numbers.

Remark 4.3: The result in Corollary 4.2, is a generalization of the above stated Theorem 1.2, for $m = 1$, due to Li and Owa [6].

Remark 4.4: For $\alpha = \frac{1}{n+1}$ and $\lambda = \frac{1-n}{2}$ in Corollary 4.2, we obtain the above stated Theorem 1.1, for $m = 1$, of Li and Owa [6] in subordination form which is more general than its existing form.

When we select $\alpha = \frac{1}{n+1}$, in Corollary 4.2, we obtain the following result.

Corollary 4.5: If $f \in \mathcal{S}_n(\alpha)$, then

$$\left(\frac{D^n[f](z)}{z} \right)^{\frac{1}{n+1}} \prec (1-z)^{\frac{2(\alpha-1)}{n+1}}, z \in \mathbb{E},$$

where $\alpha \neq 1$, is real number.

Remark 4.6: The result in Corollary 4.5, sharpens the result of Uralegaddi [2] and generalizes the result of Li and Owa [6]. For $\alpha = 0$, in Corollary 4.5, we obtain the Corollary 1, due to Li and Owa [6] for $m = 1$, in subordination form which is more general than its existing form.

If we select, $n = 0$ in Corollary 4.2, we have the following result.

Corollary 4.7: If $f \in \mathcal{A}$ satisfies

$$\frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} \prec \frac{1+(1-2\alpha)z}{1-z}, z \in \mathbb{E},$$

then

$$\left(\frac{f(z)}{z} \right)^\beta \prec (1-z)^{2\beta(\alpha-1)}, z \in \mathbb{E},$$

where $\alpha \neq 1$, $\lambda > 0$, are real numbers.

Remark 4.8: The result in Corollary 4.7, is more general than the result due Miller and Mocanu [11], Golusin [4] and Li and Owa [6], which can be obtained by selecting $\alpha = 0$ and $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. A. Uralegaddi and C. Somanatha, *Certain classes of univalent functions*, in Current Topics in Analytic Function Theory, H. M. Srivastava and S. Owa (ed.), World Scientific, Singapore, (1992), 371-374.
- [2] B. A. Uralegaddi, *Certain subclasses of analytic functions*, New Trends In Geometric Functions Theory and Applications. (Madras, 1990) 159-161, World Scientific Publishing Company, Singapore, New Jersey, London and Hong Kong, 1991.
- [3] Ch. Pommerenke, *Univalent Functions*, Vanderhoeck and Ruprecht, Göttingen, 1975.
- [4] G. M. Golusin, *Some estimates for coefficients of univalent functions*, (Russian), Math.Sb., **2**(1938), No. 3(45), 321-330.
- [5] G. S. Sălăgean, *Subclasses of univalent functions*, Lecture Notes in Math., **1013**, 362-372, Springer-Verlag, Heideberg, 1983.
- [6] Jian Li and S. Owa, *Properties of the Sălăgean operator*, Georgian Math. J., **5**(4)(1998), 361-366.
- [7] N. E. Cho and H. M. Srivastava, *Argument estimates of certain analytic functions defined by a class of multiplier transformations*, Math. Comput. Modelling, **37**(2003), 39-49.
- [8] N. E. Cho and T. H. Kim, *Multiplier transformations and strongly close-to-convex functions*, Bull. Korean Math. Soc., **40**(2003), 399-410.
- [9] R. Aghalary, R. M. Ali, S. B. Joshi and V. Ravichandran, *Inequalities for analytic functions defined by certain linear operators*, Int. J. Math. Sci., **4**(2005), 267-274.
- [10] S. Owa, C. Y. Shen and M. Obradović, *Certain subclasses of analytic functions*, Tamkang J. Math., **20**(1989), 105-115.
- [11] S. S. Miller and P. T. Mocanu, *Second-order differential inequalities in the complex plane*, J. Math. Anal. Appl., **65**(1978), 289-305.
- [12] S. S. Miller and P. T. Mocanu, *Differential subordination and Univalent functions*, Michigan Math. J., **28**(1981), 157-171.
- [13] Miller, S. S. and Mocanu, P.T., *Differential Subordinations : Theory and Applications, Series on monographs and textbooks in pure and applied mathematics* (No. **225**), Marcel Dekker, New York and Basel, 2000.